

OBPDC 2024

2-4 October 2024

Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain

Biography Presenter

Session Name	AI for data reduction
Day of the presentation	
Paper / Presentation Title	Visual image analysis of high-rate local fixed-quality compression with neural networks

Name Presenter	Sebastià Mijares
Nationality Presenter	Spain
Affiliation Presenter and Location (City, Country)	Institut d'Estudis Espacials de Catalunya (IEEC), Barcelona
Present Position	Research engineer
Name of other entities involved in the paper	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) Centre National d'Études Spatiales (CNES) École nationale supérieure d'électrotechnique, d'électronique, d'informatique, d'hydraulique et des télécommunications (INP-ENSEEIH) ISAE-SUPAERO
Experience related to the presentation (Max 150 words)	Sebastià Mijares received a Ph.D. in Computer Science from the UAB in 2024 on remote sensing data compression with neural networks. He is currently a research engineer at IEEC developing ML-based fixed-quality compression for onboard deployment in NewSpace missions.